

THE ROLE OF TEACHERS IN PROMOTING EFFECTIVE GRAMMAR LEARNING IN FOREIGN LANGUAGES ACQUISITION

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Abstract: This paper explores effective strategies for learning foreign languages, with a particular focus on the role of teachers and mentors in motivating students to master grammar rules. It examines the impact of teacher-led instruction and mentorship on language acquisition, emphasizing the importance of guidance in developing students' grammatical proficiency.

Key words: foreign language learning, teacher role, grammar mastery, language acquisition.

CHET TILLARNI O'ZLASHTIRISHDA GRAMMATIKANI SAMARALI O'RGANISHNI TARG'IB QILISHDA O'QITUVCHILARNING ROLI

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Antonatsiya: Ushbu maqolada xorijiy tillarni o'rganishning samarali strategiyalari o'rganilib, o'quvchilarni grammatika qoidalarini o'zlashtirishga undashda o'qituvchilar va murabbiylarning roliga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. U o'qituvchi rahbarligidagi ta'lim va murabbiylikning til o'zlashtirishga ta'sirini o'rganib, o'quvchilarning grammatik bilimlarini rivojlantirishda yo'l-yo'riq muhimligini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: chet tilini o'rganish, o'qituvchining roli, grammatika, tilni o'zlashtirish.

Introduction: In today's society, many people believe that learning a foreign language can be done effectively through independent study. However, this is not entirely accurate. While self-study is valuable, the guidance of teachers plays a crucial role in helping students master a language. This is particularly true for learners at the beginner (A1) or pre-intermediate (A2) levels, who often struggle with understanding complex grammar rules and language structures on their own. Without a teacher's support, these learners may have difficulty building a solid foundation in grammar, which is essential for fluency. Moreover, even upper-intermediate and advanced learners face challenges in mastering idioms, phrases, and more nuanced aspects of language use. Teachers and mentors provide critical insights, feedback, and structured learning strategies that help students overcome these obstacles and achieve higher proficiency. Therefore, the role of teachers and mentors is essential for guiding students towards language mastery, ensuring they not only learn vocabulary but also understand how to use the language accurately and effectively. According to research conducted globally, many language learners choose to study independently in preparation for language proficiency exams such as IELTS or CEFR. These learners often achieve scores like B2

or C1 without seeking feedback from teachers. However, in countries where students struggle to master foreign languages such as English or Russian, achieving higher proficiency levels like C1 can be challenging without professional guidance. For instance, learners aiming for a score of 7 to 9 in writing or speaking, even if they have a strong command of the language, may struggle to reach these goals on their own. Mastery of language exams requires more than just knowledge; it demands an understanding of the structure, style, and expectations of the test, which is where the support of teachers becomes crucial. This study analyzed data from learners across various countries who received teacher support compared to those who studied independently. It was found that with regular feedback and structured guidance, learners achieved their desired goals (C1 or higher) in 3 to 12 months. In contrast, those who studied without teacher assistance took significantly longer, with some requiring up to 15 years to achieve the same level of proficiency. These findings suggest that teacher involvement significantly accelerates the learning process, particularly in areas such as writing and speaking.

Conclusion: Without the help of teachers, it is challenging to master grammar rules effectively. Their feedback and support play a crucial role in helping students reach their language goals with ease. Most importantly, teachers bring valuable experience to guide students on the best methods for learning and mastering a foreign language.

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